

Anthelmintic Effects of Betel Nut and Tamarind Seeds to Free-Range Chicken

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Abstract:

Internal parasites are a common problem in poultry production especially for free-range chickens, this study sought to evaluate the efficacy of Betel nut and Tamarind seeds as anthelmintic to free-range chickens at different levels. Also to determine the growth performance of free-range chickens as affected by the Betel nut and Tamarind seeds, identify the species of helminths present in the experimental animals. The study was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The experimental birds were divided into 8 treatment combinations replicated thrice as follows: T1- (no dewormer applied), T2 (commercial anthelmintic), T3 (Betel nut at 5 grams), T4 (Betel nut at 10 grams), T5- (Betel nut at 15 grams), T6 – (Tamarind seeds at 5 grams), T7 – (Tamarind seeds at 10 grams), and T8 – (Tamarind seeds at 15 grams). Results revealed that experimental birds treated with Betel nut at 15 grams were the best as natural anthelmintic and most effective on the growth performance since it was comparable to that of the experimental birds in commercial anthelmintic as revealed on the frequency count of parasitic eggs and adult parasites, therefore, the study suggested the use of Betel nut at 15 grams level as a natural anthelmintic and growth promoter to Free-Range chicken.

dewormer applied), T2 (commercial anthelmintic), T3 (Betel nut at 5 grams), T4 (Betel nut at 10 grams), T5- (Betel nut at 15 grams), T6 – (Tamarind seeds at 5 grams), T7 – (Tamarind seeds at 10 grams), and T8 – (Tamarind seeds at 15 grams). Results revealed that experimental birds treated with Betel nut at 15 grams were the best as natural anthelmintic and most effective on the growth performance since it was comparable to that of the experimental birds in commercial anthelmintic as revealed on the frequency count of parasitic eggs and adult parasites, therefore, the study suggested the use of Betel nut at 15 grams level as a natural anthelmintic and growth promoter to Free-Range chicken.

Keywords: powdered natural anthelmintic, free-range chickens, feed conversion, Frequency count, helminthes, fecalysis.

Introduction

Chickens are one of the most essential sources of protein. Native chicken meat has a unique texture and flavor that the consumers choose and pay for a reasonable price, serving native chicken is a profitable commodity since the taste of its meat is excellent.

Internal parasites in poultry are not uncommon in the Philippines. For several years internal parasites such as roundworms have been known to cause serious diseases in poultry. This disease was one of the major threats to poultry particularly in Free-range chicken production due to its widespread distribution where significant may occur. The main way of

controlling nematode parasites has been with the use of synthetic anthelmintic.

However, these drugs may not be readily available to smallholder farmers or remote pastoralist communities. Furthermore, applying an unnaturally prepared dewormer to eliminate parasites may result in a remarkable increase in resistance and the introduction of new molecules through animal feces to the environment.

Therefore, using a natural anti-parasitic plant, animals can be more effectively treated at any age without risks and safe for human consumption.

Among the identified herbal plants that had potential as anthelmintic was the Betel nut (*Areca*

catechu) generally known as “Bunga”. The Betel nut contains arecoline which is a veterinary anthelmintic. Arecoline known as an alkaloid has been shown to have an indirect impact on the levels of catecholamine. Which guvacine and areaidine prevent gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptor uptake in micromolar concentrations.

Approximately 0.2 % to 1.7% by weight alkaloid compounds contain areca nut. Approximately 40-85 percent is arecoline of that amount, 10 to 40 percent is arecaidine and guvacine is 2 to 30 percent. Other alkaloids present include guvacoline and areaolidine

Another herbal plant that can be used as an anthelmintic for animals is tamarind seeds. The Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*) seed powder in any process is used in the animal and pet industry due to the anthelmintic properties it exhibits. It has also a good level of anti-bacterial function which will provide good resistance for animals. Also, a mild decoction of the pulp, when given to the animals, helps in eliminating worms and other intestinal parasites.

Herbs medicine has been used to boost the issue of internal parasites back to nature, combined with the constant crisis in economics, has lowered the power of purchasing modern medicine. Natural anthelmintics are also shown to have no negative side effects.

Hence, information on natural anthelmintics against internal parasites of poultry and livestock can fill the gap in enhancing the production and utilization of free-range chickens aside from information on improved management systems, feeding, and the occurrence of parasites and diseases. The use anti anti-parasitic plants is a vital input to the health programs that aim to control or reduce the parasitic diseases affecting free-range chickens.

In this study, the researcher tried to find out the efficiency of powdered mature betel nut and tamarind seeds as natural anthelmintic, growth enhancers to free-range chicken within 4 weeks limitation, and as distractant to internal parasites specifically to *Ascaradia galli*.

Materials and Methods

This study employed the experimental design of research and was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD).

A total of 120 heads of uniform-sized free-range chicken regardless of sex was purposively used in vivo. While the in vitro used the *Ascaradia galli* worm.

Allotment of treatment in each experimental cage was done using a table of random numbers after 2 weeks of brooding and 4 weeks of free rearing. Initial fecalysis was conducted before the anthelmintic administration. Initial weighing was also conducted to ensure that all the experimental birds were uniform in weight at the start of the study. The free-range chickens were distributed to 8 treatment combinations (T1-no anthelmintic applied, T2- commercial anthelmintic, T3- Betel nut at 5 grams, T4-Betel nut at 10 grams, T5- Betel nut at 15 grams, T6, Tamarind seeds at 5 grams, T7- Tamarind seeds at 10 grams, T8 Tamarind seeds at 15 grams) with 3 replications. These were administered with powdered betel nut and tamarind seeds at different dosages corresponding to each treatment.

Results

Frequency Count of Parasitic Eggs as Affected by the Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic

Table 1 shows the efficacy of the different kinds of powdered anthelmintic at different levels based on the egg per gram count of parasitic eggs expelled from the experimental animals from week 1 to week 4 of the study.

The average percent reduction in egg per gram count of *Ascaradia galli* in free-range chickens showed that at week 1, birds treated with commercial anthelmintic had the highest mean of 19.67 percent, followed by Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 19.33, Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 9.33, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 8.33, Tamarind seeds at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of 7.00, Tamarind seeds at 15grams (T8) with a mean of 6.67,

Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 6.33 and no anthelmintic applied (T1) with the lowest mean of 1.00. Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant result. This proves that Commercial anthelmintic (T2) and Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) have an anthelmintic

comparable effect in the first week of administration. This implies that administering Betel nut at 15 grams effectively expels parasitic eggs at the first week of administration and has the equivalent effect on commercial anthelmintic.

Table 1. Frequency Count of Parasitic Eggs as Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic

Treatments	week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
T1-No Anthelmintic Applied	1.00d	1.00e	2.33b	2.33bc
T2- Commercial Anthelmintic	19.67a	21.00a	0.00c	0.00c
T3- 5 grams (Betel Nut)	8.33bc	10.33bc	5.33a	3.67ab
T4- 10 grams (Betel Nut)	9.33b	12.00b	5.33a	3.67ab
T5- 15 grams (Betel Nut)	19.33a	18.67a	0.33c	0.00c
T6- 5 grams (Tamarind Seed)	6.33c	6.67d	7.00a	5.67a
T7- 10 grams (Tamarind Seed)	7.00c	7.00cd	7.00a	5.33a
T8- 15 grams (Tamarind Seed)	6.67c	7.00cd	5.33a	3.67ab
F-Test	**	**	**	**
CV(%)	8.14	11.71	16.58	28.47

On Week 2 post-treatment, Commercial anthelmintic(T2) obtained the highest mean of 21.00, followed by Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 18.67, Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 12.00, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 10.33, Tamarind seeds at 10 and 15 grams respectively (T7 and T8) with a mean of 7.00, Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 6.67, while no anthelmintic applied (T1) obtained the lowest mean of 1.00.

Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant result. This implies that the efficacy of betel nut at 15 grams (T5) was comparable to commercial anthelmintic at week 2 of administration, while the betel nut at different grams had a highly significant difference as well to tamarind seeds compared to betel nut shows a highly significant difference in week 2.

On week 3 post-treatment, Tamarind seed at 5 grams and 10 grams (T6 and T7) had a mean of 7.00, followed by Betel nut at 5 and 10 grams, Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T3, T4, and T8) with a mean of 5.33 respectively and no anthelmintic applied (T1) with a mean of 2.33, while Commercial anthelmintic and betel nut at 15 grams (T5 and T2) obtained the lowest mean of 0.00. Analysis of variance shows highly

significant results which means that betel nut at 15 grams and commercial anthelmintic had expelled the parasitic eggs at the first and 2nd week of treatment administration therefore experimental birds at T2 and T5 were already free from parasitic eggs while the other treatments shows that the presence of parasitic eggs is still visible.

On the 4th week post-treatment, Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) obtained the highest mean of 5.67, followed by Tamarind seeds at 10 grams(T7) with a mean of 5.33, Betel nut at 5 and 10 grams, Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T3, T4, and T8) with a mean of 3.67 respectively, no anthelmintic applied (T1) with a mean of 2.33, while the commercial anthelmintic and Betel nut at 15 grams (T2 and T5) obtained the lowest mean of 0.00. Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant difference. This implies that the presence of parasitic eggs to Betel nut at 15 grams (T2), commercial anthelmintic, and Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) were not visible in the 4th week of treatment administration, while the other treatment shows the existence of parasitic eggs in the 4th week of the study. Hence, the efficacy of betel nut at 15 grams was effective in expelling parasitic eggs at the first two weeks of treatment administration and therefore birds on

the treatment were free from parasitic eggs from week 3 to week 4.

Frequency Count of Adult Parasites as Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic

The table 2 shows that on week 1 post-treatment, commercial anthelmintic (T2)

obtained the highest efficacy mean of 4.00, followed by Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 3.67, Betel nut at 5 and 10 grams (T3 and T4) with a mean of 2.33, Tamarind seeds at 10 and 15 grams (T7 and T8) with a mean of 2.00, Tamarind seed at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 1.67, while the no anthelmintic applied (T1) obtained the lowest mean of 0.33.

Table 2. Frequency Count of Adult Parasites as Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic

Treatments	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
T1-No Anthelmintic Applied	0.33e	0.67b	0.67ab	0.67bc
T2- Commercial Anthelmintic	4.00a	4.00a	0.00b	0.00c
T3- 5 grams (Betel Nut)	2.33c	2.33ab	1.33a	1.67a
T4- 10 grams (Betel Nut)	2.33c	2.67ab	1.33a	1.00ab
T5- 15 grams (Betel Nut)	3.67b	4.00a	0.00b	0.00c
T6- 5 grams (Tamarind Seed)	1.67d	1.67ab	1.33a	1.33ab
T7- 10 grams (Tamarind Seed)	2.00c	2.00ab	1.00ab	1.00ab
T8- 15 grams (Tamarind Seed)	2.00c	2.33ab	1.33a	1.00ab
F-Test	**	**	**	**
CV(%)	42.00	42.34	52.16	42.43

ANOVA revealed a highly significant result. The results indicate that betel nut and tamarind seeds started to show anthelmintic properties however there is a highly significant difference among levels as the betel nut at 15 grams (T5) was comparable to commercial anthelmintic (T2), betel nut at 5 and 10 grams (T3 and T4) respectively, tamarind seed at 10 and 15 grams (T6 and T7) exhibit an effective level efficacy while the rest of the treatments did not meet the efficacy level as set by the standard guidelines by FAO 1999.

On week 2 post-treatment also shows that the Commercial anthelmintic and betel nut 15 grams (T2 and T5) obtained the highest mean of 4.00a, followed by Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 2.67, Betel nut at 5 grams and Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T3 and T7) with a mean of 2.33ab, Tamarind seed at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of 10 grams, Tamarind seed at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 1.67, while the no anthelmintic applied (T1) obtained the lowest mean of 0.67b.

Analysis of variance revealed a significant result. This indicates that the betel nut at 15 grams can

expel gastrointestinal parasites at week 2 as effectively as commercial anthelmintic, while the Betel nut at 5 and 10 grams (T4 and T5), Tamarind seeds at 5,10, and 15 grams (T6, T7, and T8) exhibit a 60-80 percent reduction.

On the same table at week 3 post-treatment, betel nut at 5 and 10 grams, tamarind seeds at 5 and 15 grams respectively (T3, T4, T6, T8) obtained a higher mean of 1.33a, followed by Tamarind seed at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of 1.00ab, no anthelmintic applied (T1) with a mean of 0.67ab, while the commercial anthelmintic and Betel nut at 15 grams (T2 and T5) acquire the lowest mean of 0.00b.

Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant result. This means that both experimental animals on T2 and T5 already cleared out from internal parasites, while the other treatment still shows the presence of internal parasites from the experimental animals.

On week 4 post-treatment, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) obtained the highest mean of 1.67a, preceded by Tamarind seeds at 5 and 15 grams (T6 and T8) Betel nut at 10 grams (T4), no anthelmintic applied (T1), while the Commercial

anthelmintic and Betel nut at 15 grams (T2 and T5) with a mean of 0.00c obtained the lowest mean. Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant difference.

Growth Performance

Table 3 shows the growth performance of free-range chickens in terms of initial weight, final weight, gain weight, weekly interval weights, feed consumed, feed conversion efficiency, and feed conversion ratio as affected by different levels of betel nuts and tamarind seeds.

Initial Weight

As reflected in Table 3, it reveals that the initial weight of the experimental birds ranged from 250.33 grams mean in Betel nut at 10 and 15 grams, (T4, T5) 250.26 at 5 grams and tamarind seed at 10 grams (T3 and T7) to 250.2 grams mean in no anthelmintic applied, commercial anthelmintic and tamarind seed at 15 grams (T1, T2, and T8) and Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 250.13. Variance analysis revealed no significant difference among treatment means. This implies that the birds assigned to the different treatments have comparable weight at the start of the study.

Table 3. Initial, Final, and Gain in Weight of Free-Range Chickens Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic (grams)

Treatments	Initial weight(grams)	Final weight (grams)	Gain in weight (grams)
T1-No Anthelmintic Applied	250.4	554g	303.8g
T2- Commercial Anthelmintic	251.2	936.33a	686.13a
T3- 5 grams (Betel Nut)	250.26	753.33c	503.06c
T4- 10 grams (Betel Nut)	250.33	773.66b	523.33b
T5- 15 grams (Betel Nut)	250.33	933.33a	683a
T6- 5 grams (Tamarind Seed)	250.13	618.66f	368.53f
T7- 10 grams (Tamarind Seed)	250.26	638.66e	388.4e
T8- 15 grams (Tamarind Seed)	250.2	674.33d	424.13d
F-Test	ns	**	**
CV (%)	1.32	0.75	1.13
Legend: ns- not significant *significant ** highly significant Means with the same letter are not significantly different.			

Final Weight

Table 3 reveals that the treatment means in final weight ranged from 936.33a in commercial anthelmintic (T2), followed by 933.33a in Betel nut at 15 grams (T5), 373.66b Betel nut at 10 grams (T4), 753.33c in Betel nut at 5 grams (T3), 674.33d in Tamarind seeds at 15 grams (T8), 638.66e in Tamarind seeds at 10 grams (T7), 618.66f in Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6), and the no dewormer applied (T1) with the lowest mean of 554g.

Gain in Weight

As reflected also in Table 3, the total gain in weight of free-range chickens ranged from 686.13a in commercial anthelmintic (T2) to 303.8g in no anthelmintic applied (T1). Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant difference. This implies that giving anthelmintic to free-range chickens improved the gain in weight of the chicken as the betel nuts and tamarind seeds helped to expel the parasites, however, it was also shown on the table that the experimental animals assigned to Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) has no significant difference to commercial anthelmintic (T2) where interpreted as the best treatment in terms of gain in weight.

Table 4. Weekly Weight of Free-Range Chickens as Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic (grams)

Treatments	First week weight(grams)	2nd-week weight (grams)	3rd-week weight (grams)
T1-No Anthelmintic Applied	363.40	453.00g	495.87f
T2- Commercial Anthelmintic	382.40	605.40.a	836.67a
T3- 5 grams (Betel Nut)	372.93	503.60c	606.73d
T4- 10 grams (Betel Nut)	337.73	555.93b	656.80c
T5- 15 grams (Betel Nut)	383.07	605.33a	795.33b
T6- 5 grams (Tamarind Seed)	372.13	464.73f	518.60ef
T7- 10 grams (Tamarind Seed)	373.60	475.33e	545.07e
T8- 15 grams (Tamarind Seed)	376.00	486.47d	590.67d
F-Test	ns	**	**
CV (%)	5.34	0.17	2.09

Interval Weight

First Week Birds Weight

Table shows the effects of the different anthelmintic on the interval weight on the first week of the study, the first-week interval weight of free-range chickens ranged from 383.07 grams in Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) to 337.73 grams in Betel nut at 10 grams (T4). Analysis of variance revealed that there is no significant difference between the different treatments This implies that the birds assigned to the different treatments had comparable weights on the first week of administration of the dewormer and observation.

Second Week Birds Weight

Table 4 also reflects the effect of different anthelmintics on the second week of treatment administration to free-range chickens. As seen in the table, birds from the Commercial anthelmintic (T2) obtained the highest mean of 605.40a followed by Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 605.37a, Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 555.93b, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 503.60c, Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T8) with a mean of 486.47d, Tamarind seed at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of

475.33e, Tamarind seed at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 464.73f while the no anthelmintic applied (T1) obtained the lowest mean of 453.00g. Analysis of variance revealed a highly significant result. This means that the birds administered with different anthelmintic treatments had highly affected their second-week weight.

Third Week Birds Weight

Table 4 also reflects the efficacy of different anthelmintics on the 3rd week of treatment observation of free-range chickens. Results show that birds at commercial anthelmintic (T2) obtained the highest mean of 836.67a, followed by birds in Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 795.33b, Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 653.80c, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 606.73d, Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T8) with a mean of 590.67d, Tamarind seed at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of 545.07e, Tamarind seed at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 518.60f. Experimental birds under no anthelmintic applied (T1) had the lowest mean of 495.84f grams. It was observed that there was an increase in the weight of the experimental birds at 3rd week in all treatment groups.

Table 5. Feed Consumption, Feed Conversion Efficiency, and Feed Conversion Ratio of Free-Range Chickens Affected by Different Kinds and Levels of Anthelmintic

Treatments	Feed Consumption(kg)	FCE	FCR
T1-No Anthelmintic Applied	2723.33	0.98a	1.79a
T2- Commercial Anthelmintic	2723.33	0.58g	0.79d
T3- 5 grams (Betel Nut)	2720.00	0.72e	1.08c
T4- 10 grams (Betel Nut)	2723.33	0.70f	1.04d
T5- 15 grams (Betel Nut)	2723.33	0.59g	0.80d
T6- 5 grams (Tamarind Seed)	2720.00	0.88b	1.34b
T7- 10 grams (Tamarind Seed)	2723.33	0.85c	1.40b
T8- 15 grams (Tamarind Seed)	2723.33	0.81d	1.28bc
F-Test	ns	**	**
CV (%)	0.21	0.71	7.41

Feed Consumption

Table 5 shows the growth performance of free-range chickens in terms of feed consumption, feed conversion efficiency, and feed conversion ratio as affected by different anthelmintics.

Table shows the effects of processed anthelmintic on the feed consumption of free-range chickens. It is seen on the table that the total feed consumption of free-range chickens ranged from 2723.33kg with no anthelmintic applied, commercial anthelmintic, Betel nut at 10 grams, Betel nut at 15 grams, Tamarind seeds at 10 and 15 grams (T1, T2, T4, T5, T7 and T8) to 2720.00 of Betel nut at 5 grams and Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T3 and T6). Analysis of variance reveals no significant results. This implies that administering betel nuts and tamarind seeds as herbal anthelmintic was comparable to that of commercial anthelmintic to feed consumption.

Feed Conversion Efficiency (FCE)

Table 5 shows also the feed conversion efficiency of free-range chickens in kinds and levels of anthelmintic. It reveals that experimental birds under Commercial anthelmintic (T2) were the best feed converters with a mean of 0.58g, followed by Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 0.59g, Betel nut at 10 grams (T4) with a mean of 0.70f grams, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 0.72e, Tamarind seeds at 15 grams (T8) with a mean of 0.81d, Tamarind seeds at 10 grams (T7) with a

mean of 0.85c, Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 0.88b and the highest mean obtained by no anthelmintic applied (T1) and found to be the poorest feed converters with a mean of 0.98a. However, the experimental birds under Commercial anthelmintic (T2) and Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) exhibit a not significant result to each other.

Feed Conversion Ratio

Table 5 shows also the feed conversion ratio of free-range chickens in kinds and levels of anthelmintic. It reveals that experimental birds under Commercial anthelmintic (T2) were the best feed converters with a mean of 0.79d, Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) with a mean of 0.80d, Betel nut at 10grams (T4) with a mean of 1.04cd, Betel nut at 5 grams (T3) with a mean of 1.08c, Tamarind seed at 15 grams (T8) with a mean of 1.28bc, Tamarind seeds at 5 grams (T6) with a mean of 1.34b, Tamarind seeds at 10 grams (T7) with a mean of 1.40b and the highest mean obtained by no anthelmintic applied (T1) and found to be the poorest feed converters in terms of ratio with a mean of 1.79a.

Discussion

The research probing the anthelmintic effects of betel nut and tamarind seeds on free-range chickens brings in interesting results. The study revealed the efficacy of the different anthelmintic within 4 weeks. It was then

discovered that the Betel nut at 15 grams at week 1 to week 2 was comparable in its efficacy to expel roundworms such as *Ascaridia galli* to commercial anthelmintic.

On the frequency count of parasitic eggs, and adult parasites as affected by the different kinds of anthelmintic at different levels, it was observed that betel nut at 15 grams and commercial anthelmintic were highly effective in the first and second weeks of treatment. On the other hand, the Betel nut at 10 grams was effective in the first week and second weeks. At the third week and fourth week it was observed that no presence of adult parasites in Treatment 2 and Treatment 5 based on the fecalysis conducted. While on Betel nut at 5 and 10 grams and tamarind seeds at 5,10 and 15 grams (T3, T4, T6, T7 and T8), the presence of parasitic eggs and adult parasites was present to the experimental birds throughout the study.

Likewise, the growth performance of the experimental birds, initial weight was uniform to all treatments, among all treatments the Betel nut at 15 grams (T5) and Commercial anthelmintic (T2) garnered the highest performance in terms of final weight, gain in weight, feed conversion efficiency and feed conversion ratio.

Conclusion

Based on the results and findings of the conducted study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. *Ascaridia galli*, a gastrointestinal roundworm was the only gastrointestinal helminth found in the experimental animals.
2. Using powdered betel nut at 15 grams level had the same effect as the commercial anthelmintic as highly effective at weeks 1 and 2 in expelling eggs and adult parasites of Free-Range Chicken while Tamarind seeds at all levels were found ineffective from week 1 to week 4 of the study.

3. Betel nut was more effective as a natural anthelmintic to Free- Range Chicken compared to Tamarind seed in terms of expelling parasitic eggs and adults of internal parasites within four weeks.

4. Using young betel nut at 15 grams level was the best on the growth performance of free-range chickens in terms of final weight, gain in weight, feed conversion efficiency, and feed conversion ratio.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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